

SELECTION AND CLASSIFICATION OF TYPES OF ARTWORK FOR CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article discusses the selection and classification of types of artwork for children and their importance in the educational and developmental process. The study analyzes different forms of children's artwork, including drawing, painting, collage, sculpture, and decorative arts, according to children's age, interests, and creative abilities. The article also highlights the pedagogical significance of selecting appropriate artwork activities for enhancing children's imagination, aesthetic perception, fine motor skills, and creative thinking. Furthermore, effective approaches for organizing art activities in preschool and primary education are presented.

Keywords: children's artwork, art education, creative development, classification of artwork, preschool education, visual arts, aesthetic education, creativity, fine motor skills, children's activities.

When working with preschool children, the correct selection of works of art and their classification are important factors determining the effectiveness of the pedagogical process. Works of art form the emotional, intellectual, aesthetic and social development of children, and also play a central role in the instillation of national values and the development of speech and imagination. Therefore, when choosing artistic materials, educators need to take into account the age characteristics of the child, interests, stages of development and pedagogical goals. Works of art have different forms and content, and it is important to classify them in accordance with the psychological and emotional needs of children.

Fairy tales are the most important source of children's literature, they expand children's imagination, enrich their emotional world and form moral values. Fairy tales show the courage, loyalty, friendship and honesty of the heroes, develop empathy, emotional thinking and the ability to make moral decisions in children. At the same time, fairy tales create a basis for fantasy and creative thinking in children, enrich their inner world and imagination. Stories and short stories reflect children's everyday life experience and teach moral values, social relationships and problem-solving skills through simple, understandable events.

Listening to and discussing stories helps children develop analysis, understanding of cause-and-effect relationships, and communication skills. At the same time, children perceive events through stories, understand the behavior of characters, and learn to express their thoughts. Poetry develops children's rhythmic sensitivity, language culture, and aesthetic taste. Melodious and rhythmic poems allow children to concentrate, remember the text, and improve their speech skills. At the same time, poetry develops visual perception and expands children's aesthetic thinking. Texts enriched with rhythmic and word games stimulate children's imagination and creativity.

National legends, folk tales, songs and legends form national identity, historical memory and cultural values in children. This type of material introduces children to the customs, values and historical experiences of their people. At the same time, national materials enrich the emotional and aesthetic world of children, educate them in the spirit of respect for culture. When choosing works of art, it is necessary to take into account age characteristics. Children aged 5–6 years have difficulty understanding abstract concepts, therefore, concrete, visually and emotionally enriched materials are more effective for them.

Educators are advised to consider the following criteria: the content of the text should be appropriate to the child's level of understanding, the characters should be realistic and relatable, the ability to explain through visual and illustrative elements, the ability to attract attention through rhythmic and melodic forms, and the ability to express moral, national, and social values. Thus, the selection and classification of works of art for children is a strategic pedagogical tool that serves the emotional, aesthetic, intellectual, and social development of children in the process of preschool education. Properly selected artistic materials allow children to experience national values, develop fantasy and creative thinking, form moral and social skills, and make an important contribution to their development as individuals.

The selection and classification of works of art in working with preschool children has a purely pedagogical value, being a key tool in the processes of emotional and social development of the child, speech abilities, the formation of fantasy and aesthetic taste, as well as the awakening of national feelings. The correct selection of works of art is the selection of literature intended for children in accordance with their age characteristics, interests, stage of psychological development and educational goals, and pedagogical theories put forward the principles of high-quality organization of this process.

One of the main pedagogical functions of works of art is to help the child understand various social and moral situations. Works of art enrich the child's inner world, shape his emotional experience through the depiction of small events, decisions of characters and social situations. Therefore, works of art are considered as a means of developing children's emotional intelligence, empathy and communication culture. When choosing works of art, their content and form should correspond to the psychological needs of children.

Fairy tales, simply put, contain small, detailed stories about the mythical world, the lives of heroes, their goals and decisions. These stories stimulate children's thinking, emotions and moral decision-making. As psychological researchers have noted, through fairy tales, a child learns to distinguish between good and evil, understands the character's situation in the course of the story and feels it in connection with his own emotions. The second type is stories and short stories, which reflect the themes directly related to children's everyday life situations. Stories help the child learn the relationship between events, cause and effect, form speech vividly, and strengthen the child's social skills by analyzing small events in reality.

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